

OPTIMIZATION OF THE REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH PARANOID SCHIZOPHRENIA**Sattarov T.**

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ABSTRACT

This article reviews studies on eating disorders in patients with paranoid schizophrenia. Psychotherapeutic methods, such as art therapy, have a beneficial effect on the mental state of patients with digestive disorders, including helping to relieve symptoms of depression. The use of methods of psychocorrection in patients contributes to a significant increase in the period of remission, as well as optimization of the rehabilitation of patients

Keywords: eating disorders, psychocorrection, paranoid schizophrenia.

Introduction. The relevance of the problem of studying eating disorders in patients with paranoid schizophrenia is one of the most important tasks of practical health care [1,3,7]. In the literature, there are very few scientific works on digestive disorders in schizophrenic patients, and they mainly investigate the clinical manifestations of this phenomenon, without focusing on gender differences and the peculiarity of clinical differences in the syndromological aspect [2,6,8]. The effectiveness of psychotherapeutic intervention in patients with paranoid schizophrenia comorbid with eating disorders remains a debatable issue in practical psychiatry to this day [4,5,9]. In pubertal patients, the presence of depressive symptoms provokes the formation of suicidal tendencies [10,11,12].

The purpose of the study was to study the effectiveness of art therapy in patients with digestive disorders occurring in the clinical picture of paranoid schizophrenia in order to improve medical and psychological care for this group of patients.

Materials and methods of the study: 37 patients with paranoid schizophrenia who were hospitalized in a psychiatric hospital were included in the study. Among them, there were 19 female patients and 18 men with eating disorders. In the course of the study, clinical-psychopathological and follow-up methods of research were used. Of the psychometric methods, the Calgary Scale, the PANSS Scale, and the Eating Attitude Test (EAT-40) were used. All examined patients underwent psycho-correctional work in the form of group sessions of art therapy (coloring with watercolor stencils, applications with grains of rice, buckwheat,

mung bean, beans, lentils) in combination with rational psychotherapy and music therapy.

Results of the study: out of 37 examined patients, 65% were diagnosed with paranoid schizophrenia with a continuous type of course F-20.00, 35% of the examined patients had paranoid schizophrenia with an episodic type of course F-20.01. Testing on the Calgary scale revealed the presence of depressive disorders in almost the entire surveyed contingent. In 55% of patients, the presence of depression of moderate severity was registered. 36% of the subjects suffered from mild depression, and only 10% of patients were diagnosed with severe depression according to the Calgary scale. Gender characteristics of digestive disorders in women were mainly represented by a tendency to overeating, the formation of metabolic syndrome. In men, eating disorders showed significant differences from women. Clinical manifestations were characterized primarily by a decrease in appetite and refusal to eat. The majority of men sought to consume biologically active dietary supplements that promote weight loss, which led to a decrease in compliance and a relapse of the endogenous process. We have experimented with the use of art therapy using anti-stress coloring stencils "Food". Prior to art therapy, all the examined patients had a level of severity of depressive symptoms. Art therapy sessions were conducted by clinical and medical psychologists in closed departments of the city clinical hospital in Tashkent with a frequency of three times a week, lasting 45-60 minutes during three months of observation of patients. Most of the male patients were happy to complete the tasks of the psychotherapist, mostly using bright warm colors during art therapy (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Creativity of male patients

Male patients, in most cases, preferred to paint stencils of meat products, fast food, and the use of natural shades of the watercolor and gouache paint palette was observed. Unlike female patients, men rarely used mosaics, appliqué, and decoration of pattern stencils with beads in an art therapy session. Females were happy to paint stencils reflecting confectionery - cakes, pastries, sweets, pizza, and bakery pastries. The longer

participation of females in group therapy sessions with creativity is explained by their perseverance, a tendency to perform routine monotonous work, greater patience and flattening of the emotional sphere. Art therapy using application methods contributed to the development of fine locomotor skills and the formation of stabilization of the psycho-emotional sphere of women (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Creativity of female patients

Unlike men, females chose cold shades of the palette of colors for coloring pictures with food, motivating their choice with aversion to food and lack of appetite. Patients in most cases combined painting stencils

with watercolors with mosaic design, appliqué, gluing grains of rice, buckwheat, and beans onto the drawings (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Combined use of art therapy methods

The combined use of art therapy methods by women was explained by the more effective effect of the relaxing component of psycho-corrective intervention. After group sessions of art therapy, there was a significant decrease in the severity of depressive pathology and a reduction in eating disorders. These studies allow optimizing a comprehensive approach to the treatment of digestive disorders in patients with paranoid schizophrenia, reducing the number of hospitalizations, prolonging remission periods and preventing possible somatic complications.

Conclusions: thus, the results obtained during the study contribute to the improvement of planning the provision of pharmacotherapy in combination with psychotherapy. The used integrative methods of psychotherapy for patients with paranoid schizophrenia, taking into account gender differences in psychiatric hospitals, will help optimize the rehabilitation of patients with eating disorders, reduce the number of hospitalizations and maximize the remission period.

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